

Integral Criteria for the State of the Enterprise and their Role in Management (Review)

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Abstract

Integral criteria for monitoring the state of an enterprise. Integral criteria prototype – characteristic dependencies from neurophysiology. The examples of obtaining and using integral criteria is given possible integral criteria in trade, industry, in finance (banking system). According to the differences of the Integral Criteria (IC) – classification of management systems. The use of Integral Criteria makes it possible to recognize and classify economic and financial systems without interfering with these systems. On five examples from different fields of science and technology, the universality of the principle of neurophysiology was shown, and this principle was presented as a new principle of bionics. Five examples (repetitions) of the same similarity are to justify the universality of the new principle and its use in economics, finance and management sciences, which was done. ICs provide not only optimal operating modes of the system, but ICs also allow you to determine the number of participants in the system, as well as classify each participant. At the same time, participants are recognized by their external features, which are not perceived by the participants themselves. IC is a characteristic feature of the system.

Keywords: Integral criteria, Neurophysiology, Business, Trade, Finance, Banking system, Exchange business, Bionics, Black box.

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1. Introduction

The surgical, effective, and objective control for the enterprise state expediently is realized on a base of the integral criterions (IC). It is necessary some information about an enterprise and its interaction with surrounding outside for a determination IC. The data of bookkeeping calculation are sufficient for it. Relation to the enterprise is constructed according to the principle of a black box. The analog for IC is an extremum on the functional dependence "energy – duration" from neurophysiology. The experience of using this extremum in various fields of science and technology is considered: only 5 examples, which are also analogues in the description of IC.

IC provides recognition of systems by responses from external influences: managerial or operational.

2. Methods

The determination of IC is based on building of a characteristic dependence. For the first time such dependences are discovered in neurophysiology [1] was further discovered their universality and validity for all functioning systems, including all technical. [2]

Research carried out showed that all living systems have regimes (conditions) of minimum expenditures upon reaching (achievement) of the specific result, necessary for the vital activity. Under these conditions the physiological state of living system to the adequately environment. It is analogous, in the technical systems (enterprises, devices, exchanges, banks,...): construction (design) state, the wear of the fixed capital, information – administrative guarantee, the regime (conditions) of the work of personnel and the fitness for work of individual workers must be adequate to environment. Any deviations from the regime (conditions) of minimum expenditures signal about the damage of the adequacy of interaction of technical system and environment. The IC states of technical system and its interaction with the environment are the parameters of this regime (conditions).

Generalization of the accumulated results of the use of IC based on the principle of analogies allowed us to expand the experience gained in using IC, and extend this experience to the management of economics, finance, and management.

3. Examples of using the proposed IC

3.1. Biotechnology and bionics

Estimation of effectiveness of feeding of living organisms for reaching the greatest growing and the best state of their health. [3]

Misfeeding or overfeeding is equally undesirable. Determination of "golden middle" makes free – from whole series of other problems:

- control for their health status and treatment of the organisms;
- utilization of excessive wastes;
- production and delivery of superfluous feed ...

Determination of chemical components of admixtures in water without facilities of analytical chemistry. [4]

3.2. Metal processing technology

The IR principle was used in mechanical engineering to determine the adequate mode of metal processing. [5]

3.3 Determination of Integral Criterion in economics, finance and management

In cybernetics and in bionics IC are defined as extrema of functional dependences of values of threshold "useful results" from time of cycle of vital activity. [1, 2]

Also, when analyzing water, determining the optimal mode of feeding living organisms and optimal mode of metal processing. [3-5]

These five examples using the axonometric method indicate the versatility of the proposed IC. Based on this, this principle is used in economics, finance, and management to define IP. Here IC are extremum of function of expenditures for unit of products with respect to time of operating cycle (period of production of unit of products or time of its realization). Necessary data for IC obtaining can be obtained from reports of administrative or bookkeeping calculation.

Following are the three steps to obtain an IC for specific cases.

Figure 1: Dependence f of expenditures 3 for unit of activity ed is $\frac{3}{ed}$ or $3/ed$ on volume of activity (issue, product) – V_{pr} . [6] $\frac{3}{ed} = f(V_{pr})$,

Source: Author.

where a is constants expenditure for unit of product, b is variables expenditure for unit of products.

Figure 2: Determination of the integral criterion.

Source: Author.

Where

$$\frac{1}{V'_{np}} = \frac{dT}{dV_{np}} = \frac{T}{ed \cdot np} \quad (2)$$

is the period of the production of unit for $ed \cdot np$, x and Y_{min} is the coordinate of IC .

Figure 3: For clarity, the IC function argument $\frac{1}{V'_{np}} = \frac{T}{ed \cdot np}$ converted to the logarithmic scale $Lg(T/ed \cdot np)$.

Source: Author.

The Point with the coordinate of

$$x = Lg(T/ed \cdot np) \quad (3)$$

and $y = Y_{min}$ is the most attractive regime (conditions) of the work of enterprise IC. In this case expenditure for the unit of output or realized goods is minimum.

3.4 Possible IC in the trade and the industry, financing, management

Minimum costs per unit of production, financing, management – accompanied by:

- by minimum load on the enterprise (executive system), with the retention (maintaining) of the volumes of production and quality of production;
- by the minimum wear of its fixed capital;
- the least amount of waste;
- by the reduction of reject ...;
- by an increase in the profitability;
- productivity of labor.

IC can be basic for determining the regime (conditions) of the optimum work of devices

(machine tools, apparatuses ...) and enterprises (industrial, financial ...). In the trade and in the social sphere of IC can be auxiliary or those generalizing during the prognostication. The fact is that the trade is conjugated (combined) with the price and commercial policy. In several cases the policy, having the prevailing value, can direct the work of enterprise into the mode of unfavorable operation.

Trade enterprises produce nothing, but they only transfer goods from the producer to the user, i.e., are fulfilled the functions of mediator. Target (purpose) – satisfaction of the demands of user and obtaining profit. Each commercial enterprise it finds and develops its methods and ways of the commodity transfer to user. In spite of differences, the essence of the process of wholesale and retail trade in one and characteristic of the success of this process they are identical. Consequently IC, which make it possible to evaluate the work of this process, will identical.

For example, to select an IC at trade enterprises, it is necessary to determine:

- conditional energy reduced to a product, necessary for its promotion to the counter, sale, and after-sales service (the minimum of this energy is the highest efficiency of trade, i.e., IC);
- conditional energy reduced to finance (the minimum of this energy is IC, which leads to a stable and highest residual value);
- conditional energy of movement of buyers (minimum of this energy – IC customer service), etc.

Concept industrial enterprise includes the enormous variety:

- enterprises can relate to different branches of industry (from that obtaining to the aviation);
- enterprises, which relate to one branch, can work in the broad bands of technological processes, power-weight ratio, and extent of outfitting by equipment;
- enterprise can be small, large, and giant;
- enterprises can be commercial and non-commercial;

- enterprises have different collections of the interrelated targets (purposes), ...

Therefore, development and detection of IC, the characteristic and forecasting activity enterprises, must be carried out for each enterprise, industry, financing, and management separately.

3.5 Stock exchange matter

The regularity proposed is partially defined and is adapted during the definition of the value of the assumed future profitableness (implied forward yield) as time derivative of the inverted curve of profitableness (inverted yield curve) on the market for percent (rates in the brokers matter). [7]

$$I_{FR} = \frac{LI - S + i}{L - S} \quad (01)$$

where I_{FR} is assumed future value, I is the rate of longer-lived of financial tools, i is the rate of shorter of financial tools, L is period of the action of longer-term of financial tools, S is period of the action of shorter of financial tools.

Graphically it is possible to obtain the dependence, which indicates regime (conditions) adequate to the conditions of market. In this regime (conditions) it is possible to have the best value, and it is possible to improve all the remaining parameters.

Use by IC, in the near future, can have an effect on the modernization of industry, financing, management commercial and production technologies, and also enterprises themselves.

4. History

For the first time, a description of this topic was presented in 1969. The principle inherent in threshold systems is the law of minimum energy (the bionic principle). [8]

Based on a number of uses of the functional dependence of strength-duration, using the principle of analogy, using examples of graphical dependencies, the possibilities of using the derived functions to manage economic processes were indicated, 2003. [9]

5. Perspectives

It is experimentally established that in a number of cases, the graphic dependence indicates not one IC, but by several. The fact is that some

processes, which we receive, as uniform (single function), in reality depend on many factors, each of which has their IC. In such cases the procedure of the determination of IC proposed is applicable for the analysis of the structure of the dependences of the state of the controlled (inspected) objects.

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6. Conclusion

ICs provide not only optimal operating modes of the system, but ICs also allow you to determine the number of participants in the system, as well as classify each participant. At the same time, participants are recognized by their external features, which are not perceived by the participants themselves. IC is a characteristic feature of the system.

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